

Developing and measuring targets for reducing wildfire risk in Europe

Abstract

The impact of wildfires is increasing worldwide. This does not only concern the area burned but also the losses resulting from areas affected. While the root causes of these effects are manifold, encompassing among others the accumulation of fuels or increasing settlements in wildland-urban interfaces (WUI), events over the last decade point also towards the emergence of novel extreme wildfire events not reported previously. Reports and initiatives to better understand and counteract these developments have been launched recently, including for example the *Landscape Governance Framework*, the *Wildfire Peer Review Assessment Framework* (PRAF) by the European Commission's Directorate General for Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection (DG ECHO) or reports by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) or the Global Fire Management Hub Initiative by the Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO 2023).

In parallel to this, large research and development investments are launched with the same aim. In the European context, more than 60 Million € have been invested under the Green Deal to understand and manage extreme wildfire risk. This investment has been coupled with wildfire risk management targets related to the reduction of fatalities, losses and emissions.

This example shows that the development of (quantitative) wildfire risk management targets can be a useful way in determining overall goals, for developing means to achieve them as well as for monitoring progress. However, the development, implementation and monitoring of targets also raise challenges in terms of normative and technical questions such as data availability or the scale of targets.

Building on the Green Deal research targets, this article discusses open questions related to wildfire risk management targets with the aim to inform discourses related to wildfire risk management targets that could result from the need to develop more integrated approaches as suggested by the mentioned policy documents and reports, with a focus on the European context.

1 Introduction

Anthropogenic climate change and landscape transformation are altering the dynamics of extreme wildfire events (Sullivan et al. 2022; Rossi et al. 2020; Chergui et al. 2018 or Tollefson 2024). The year 2023 illustrated how more common extreme fires could look like as the number of hectares burned broke many records worldwide. To name just two examples, in Canada, more than 13 million hectares had burned by August (NASA Earth Observatory 2023). In July 2023, devastating fires swept through Rhodes, Corfu, and the Athens area, followed by numerous wildfires in August across Greece. The most severe blaze occurred near Alexandroupoli in the northeast Greece, close to the Turkish border. Ignited on 19 August, the fire raged for days due to dry vegetation, strong winds, and high temperatures. EFFIS reports indicate that more than 94,000 hectares of natural land were destroyed in this fire alone. Greece saw over 45,000 hectares of forests and 62,000 hectares within a Natura 2000 biodiversity reserve, including the Dadia-Lefkimi-Soufli Forest National Park, consumed by the flames. The wildfire in Dadia, Greece is the largest in the EU since 2000, when the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) began recording data (Joint Research Centre (JRC) 2023). Early 2024, devastating wildfires hit central Chile's Valparaíso region due to intense summer heat, destroying thousands of homes in Viña del Mar. The fires spread quickly from forested areas to populated zones despite containment efforts,

consuming 8,500 hectares of land and 6,000 homes. The extreme heatwave, attributed to climate change and El Niño, also impacted other parts of South America, prompting residents to seek relief in coastal areas (NASA Earth Observatory 2024). Over the past decade, wildfire events around the globe (e.g., 2016 in Canada; 2017 in Chile, USA, and Portugal; 2018 in Northern Europe, South Africa and the USA; 2019 in Bolivia; 2020 in Australia and USA) point to the emergence of novel extreme wildfire events not reported previously and associated, in many areas, to a higher frequency of events than expected (Duane et al. 2021). The number of losses is thereby drastically increasing (Swiss Re Institute 2021). In 2023, the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) closely tracked wildfires worldwide using its Global Fire Assimilation System (GFAS), providing detailed information on wildfire intensity and carbon emissions. This year record-breaking wildfire activity was observed in various regions, with Canada reporting the highest wildfire carbon emissions in the CAMS record and Greece facing its largest wildfire within the European Union since record. Global wildfires collectively produced around 2,170 megatonnes of carbon emissions, with Canadian wildfires contributing 22% of this total (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service 2024).

Other natural hazards and extreme weather events have also increased in the past 70 years (Vautard et al. 2023), such as floods and heatwaves, for example. For several hazards risk reduction targets have hence been developed. While targets for wildfires under the Green Deal have been suggested with numerical values, targets for earthquakes, heat waves or floods are frequently defined qualitatively and cannot be verified using fixed numbers. Reducing the effects of earthquakes, the aim is for example to enforce seismic design regulations. These are to be based on ground motion values for predefined periods and thus regulate how buildings must be constructed in order to withstand possible ground shaking (Douglas et al. 2015). Targets regarding significant temperature increases have also been defined in Europe – for example in Germany and England. The Heatwave Plan for England aims to protect the health of living beings and reduce the damage caused by extreme heat by preparing for the effects and providing people with detailed information (Policy Innovation Research Unit 2019). In Germany, the Ministry of Health's Heat Protection Plan for Health sets out four goals concerning heat events. Firstly, the population should be sensitized and secondly, deaths in connection with heat should be reduced and avoided. In addition, intervention and communication scandals should be avoided. The fourth aim is to improve and disseminate scientific evidence (Ministry of Health 27.07.2023).

1.1 New governance frameworks and reports

In an attempt to better understand such events and to develop more effective approaches to managing wildfire risk, various reports and high-level governance frameworks were released recently such as the Landscape Fire Governance Framework developed by the Portuguese Agency for Rural Fires (Portuguese Agency for Integrated Rural Fire Management (AGIF) 2023), the OECD report on “Taming Wildfires in the Context of Climate Change” (OECD 2023) or the “Spreading like Wildfire: The Rising Threat of Extraordinary Landscape Fires” by the United Nations Environment Programme (Sullivan et al. 2022).

The above cited documents argue for enhanced and more integrated governance approaches and better stakeholder integration across the relevant sectors including infrastructures and insurance. For example, AGIF (2023) calls for “enhanced governance at local, regional, national, and international levels”. “In managing risk, governance is of utmost importance, driving public and private sector agents, corporate and individual, into cross-sectoral cooperation, actively promoting work on all stages of the integrated fire management value chain.” The OECD report (2023) provides a comprehensive overview over the links between climate change and growing extreme wildfire risk as well as a range of measures to address this development by upscaling prevention measures, financing of wildfire risk prevention through a mix of public and private funding and a “whole-of-government approach in

wildfire management, i.e. a collaborative approach that addresses the complex challenge of managing wildfire risk by aligning and co-ordinating the institutional interventions of wildfire management horizontally and vertically across government”. The Wildfire Peer Review Assessment Framework by the European Commission’s Directorate General for Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection (DG ECHO) stresses the need for considering at both national and sub-national levels all phases of the disaster risk management cycle (Casartelli, V. and J. Mysiak 2023).

1.2 Lack of wildfire risk management targets

The afore-mentioned reports develop a broad range of recommendations related for example to enhance prevention measures, to better integrate the relevant stakeholders or to adapt the underlying funding mechanisms. However, none of the documents discusses the potential use of targets for enhancing wildfire risk management and the use of indicators for measuring progress is hardly discussed. While the usefulness and effectiveness of targets in governance depends on a range of contextual factors as discussed below, is still surprising that targets are not addressed as a potential measure to specify and assess wildfire risk management progress. The development of targets to achieve (international) policy goals is well established and has been applied for example to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) where each of the goals is detailed by very specific targets and indicators¹ or with respect to climate change mitigation by the Paris Agreement, limiting the global temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.

In light of this, there is a critical need for further exploration and integration of targeted approaches to enhance wildfire risk management efforts, especially in regions where the impact of wildfires poses significant challenges to UN SDGs and climate change mitigation initiatives as seen in Figure 1 (Martin, 2019; Source: Kurvits et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Impacts of wildfire on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The changing scale and intensity of wildfires may impact achievements across several of the SDGs related to human health and well-being

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> (22.02.2024).

(Martin, 2019; Source: Kurvits et al., 2022)

Building upon the established framework of setting targets for international policy goals, the incorporation of specific targets for wildfire risk management can provide a focused and strategic approach to addressing the increasing threat of wildfires. By aligning wildfire risk management efforts with measurable targets and indicators, policymakers can enhance the effectiveness of mitigation strategies, improve preparedness and response mechanisms, and ultimately reduce the socio-economic and environmental impacts of wildfires. This targeted approach can also facilitate better coordination among stakeholders, foster innovation in risk reduction measures, and promote adaptive governance practices to address the complex challenges posed by wildfires in a changing climate and landscape. Overall, integrating targeted approaches into wildfire risk management can contribute to achieving SDGs, advancing climate resilience, and protecting vulnerable communities and ecosystems from the devastating effects of wildfires.

For the disaster risk management context, Mitchell et al. (2014) had already recommended since 2014 that it was “important to establish clear, numerical targets at a global scale to act as eye-catching, awareness-raising components of the SDGs and the post-2015 framework on Disaster Risk Reduction, and also to help direct actions.”² In line with this, the Sendai Framework has been complemented with targets and indicators which are monitored (UNDRR, n.a.)³.

Overall, targets provide clear and measurable goals that help guide and assess the effectiveness of policies and strategies (Behn 2003) by clearly articulating specific objectives toward well-defined outcomes. This clarity establishes a shared understanding of the intended goals among stakeholders which is specifically helpful in a setting of many diverse stakeholders like the wildfire risk management context. Targets can not only support motivation and collaboration (Simmonds et al. 2020) but allow for systematic measurement of progress and success (Sayer et al. 2016) as well as for periodic reassessment and adjustment of strategies (Maron et al. 2021). This quantification may contribute towards enhancing accountability of stakeholders, the allocation of resources and finally the communication of strategies and raising public awareness.

1.3 Binding risk management targets at EU level for other hazards

In the EU context, civil protection is an area in which the Union shall have competence to carry out actions to support, coordinate or supplement the actions of the Member States (Art. 6 (f) TFEU) which remain the main civil protection authorities. Many of the activities at EU level hence facilitate the exchange of practices, networking among key stakeholders and more broadly also the generation of a knowledge base⁴. Supporting disaster risk management measures are also implemented in relation to risk assessments, training and disaster response, among others. For specific hazards however, more detailed legal frameworks were developed, namely floods and industrial accidents.

The Flood Directive (2007/60/EC) established a framework for the assessment and management of flood risks to reduce the negative consequences of flooding on human health, economic activities, the environment and cultural heritage in the European Union. According to the Directive, EU countries are required to:

- assess all areas where significant floods could take place;

² https://dial.uclouvain.be/downloader/downloader.php?pid=boreal:178839&datastream=PDF_01

³ <https://www.undrr.org/implementing-sendai-framework/monitoring-sendai-framework> (22.02.2024).

⁴ For example, Regulation (EU) 2021/836 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 amending Decision No 1313/2013/EU on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism specified that the Commission shall establish a Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network.

- map the flood extent and assets and humans at risk in these areas;
- take adequate and coordinated measures to reduce this flood risk.

The Flood Directive hence even goes beyond the specification of target values for disaster risk reduction in general and develops legally binding flood reduction measures that have to be implemented by the Member States.

In that sense, the EU regulatory framework for floods and industrial accidents is more encompassing than for other hazards. This can be explained by floods accounting for almost 43% of natural hazard impacts in terms of costs. The most expensive hazards during the period 1980-2022 include the 2021 flooding in Germany and Belgium (EUR 44 billion), the 2022 compound drought and heat events over the whole continent (EUR 40 billion), the 2002 flood in central Europe (EUR 34 billion), among others as the below figure shows.

Figure 1: Annual economic losses caused by weather - and climate - related extreme events in the EU Member States
Source: European Environment Agency (EEA) (2023).

The SEVESO III Directive⁵ lays down rules for the prevention of major accidents which involve dangerous substances, and the limitation of their consequences for human health and the environment. Historically, this Directive was the result of many incidents during the 1960s and 1970s, characterised by rapid expansion of process industry and the related use of fuels, materials, fibres, and pharmaceuticals but likewise large-scale pollution, fires, explosions, and dispersion of toxic clouds (Jain et al. 2017). This included the eponymous chemical accident in Seveso, Italy in 1976 which led to mass evacuations and dioxin poisoning of approximately 2,000 citizens.

In summary, the EU regulatory framework is most advanced in the fields where hazards had or have the largest impacts. Sadly, wildfires seem to catch-up with flood events as the number of losses is drastically increasing. According to figures by Swiss Re, the damages from wildfires are rising faster than from any other “secondary peril” which are events that generate small to mid-sized losses such as hail, flood, or storm (Swiss Re by Sinai 2022). In the last four years alone, wildfires were responsible

⁵ Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directive 96/82/EC Text with EEA relevance.

for almost a quarter of all secondary-peril insurance losses worldwide⁶, accounting for more than 20 billion USD in 2020 alone.

The increase in global wildfire events, their related losses and the expected continuation of this trend hence raise the question whether a more binding framework for wildfires, potentially including wildfire targets could be developed at European scale, before ever worse effects materialise. Research funding and expected targets

The European Green Deal dedicated around 60 Mio. € to respond to extreme wildfire events by funding three Innovation Actions (IAs) ([FIRE-RES](#), [SILVANUS](#) and [TREEADS](#) projects) and a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) ([FIRELOGUE](#) project) to facilitate the integration between the IAs and promote the sharing of knowledge between projects. According to the call, the Actions funded must:

“speed up the pan-European adaptation process to extreme wildfires by advancing and applying research and innovation, including demonstration pilot sites, while making best use of existing data (e.g., remote sensing, in-situ or community-based data), technologies (e.g., Big Data and Artificial Intelligence) and services (as Copernicus, Galileo and EGNOS). Innovative means and methods should be developed, integrated and demonstrated in different environments across Europe (including EU outermost regions) and tailored to geographical and socio-economic conditions, with different types of fuels (e.g. forest/bush /peat fire threats), landscapes and biodiversity values (e.g. coastal/alpine/agriculture/rural/Wild-Urban Interface/islands) and scales (e.g. local/regional/national/cross-border/EU/international). The approach should be systemic: encompassing different climate scenarios, biogeographical/socio-economic contexts, traditional practices and new means for faster and smarter management of all interconnected fire management phases, i.e. prevention and preparedness (including forecasting and landscape management for impact mitigation, adapting tree species composition and forest management practices), detection and response (including fire containment, extinction, potential evacuation and recovery) and post-fire restoration and adaptation to climate change.”

As mentioned in the call⁷, a set of targets by 2030 were defined for the funded projects:

- 0 fatalities from wildfires
- 50% reduction in accidental fire ignitions
- 55% reduction in emissions from wildfires
- Control of any extreme and potentially harmful wildfire in less than 24 hours
- 50% of Natura 2000 protected areas to be fire-resilient
- 50% reduction in building losses
- 90% of losses from wildfires insured
- 25% increase in surface area of prescribed fire treatments at EU level

In order to encourage the discussion around a wildfire risk management legal framework or less binding targets, this paper uses the above targets to illustrate challenges of assessing and implementing targets more generally. It seeks to provide context to the proposed target dimensions, and sketches a number of aspects that should be taken into consideration when developing targets for wildfire risk management at different governance levels including aspects of data availability and quality.

⁶ Before 2016, the share of this peril in losses averaged just above 3% and rarely exceeded 5–10%” (Swiss Re Institute 2022).

⁷ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_LC-GD-1-1-2020 (13.05.2023).

2 Challenges in defining targets for managing wildfire risk

Establishing targets for wildfire risk management is a multifaceted endeavour fraught with challenges stemming from various factors. The diverse nature of wildfire risk, influenced by factors such as climate, vegetation types, fire regimes and land use patterns, or societal readiness, complicates the task of defining effective targets. What may constitute a viable target in one region could prove unsuitable in another, highlighting the need for tailored approaches that account for the unique characteristics of specific locales. Attempting to devise standardised targets runs the risk of overlooking the nuances of individual landscapes, potentially undermining the efficacy of risk management strategies.

Moreover, the dynamic nature of wildfires introduces an additional layer of complexity to target setting. Wildfires exhibit variability over time, with historical data often proving limited or unreliable, particularly in areas where fire events are infrequent. This lack of historical context further hampers the ability to accurately assess past trends and patterns, impeding the formulation of data-driven and realistic targets for wildfire risk mitigation. The variability in wildfire behaviour underscores the importance of adopting flexible and adaptive approaches that can account for evolving fire dynamics and uncertainties.

Furthermore, the global context adds another dimension to the challenge of defining wildfire risk targets. What may be deemed appropriate and effective in one country may not necessarily align with the priorities and needs of another, necessitating a nuanced understanding of local contexts and considerations. Balancing the intricacies of climate, vegetation, land use, and historical fire data is essential in crafting targets that are robust, context-specific, and responsive to the evolving wildfire landscape. By acknowledging and addressing these complexities, stakeholders can better navigate the intricacies of wildfire risk management and develop targeted strategies that effectively mitigate the impact of wildfires across diverse regions. For example:

1. In regions with a Mediterranean climate, characterized by hot, dry summers and wet winters, wildfires often originate by the abundance of fine fuels. In particular, biomass production in these areas is high, while the decomposition rate remains sluggish. These fine fuels comprise a diverse array of flammable materials, ranging from dead grass and leaf litter to twigs, needles, bark, and even live vegetation. On the other hand, in tall Mediterranean forests, the abundance of light fosters the growth of long crowns that reach down to the surface fuels. It also promotes the development of a significant shrub understory. The distinctive landscape of Mediterranean regions, featuring sparse forests interspersed and pockets of open spaces interspersed within the forest areas, provides an optimal environment for the rapid propagation of wildfires. Moreover, the undulating topography of these areas, with high mountains, hills and valleys, facilitates the swift spread of fires, propelled by wind patterns and terrain configurations.

Conversely, regions with temperate climates and dense forests present a contrasting scenario. Here, the primary concern often revolves around the looming threat of crown fires, which rapidly engulf the forest canopy and cause widespread devastation. Unlike Mediterranean regions, where fine fuels prevail, temperate regions with their dense forest cover pose distinct challenges for wildfire management. The complex interplay between climate, vegetation density, and fire behaviour requires tailored fuel reduction strategies. A one-size-fits-all approach to fuel reduction across Mediterranean and temperate regions may prove inadequate to address the specific risks unique to each ecosystem. Therefore, a nuanced understanding of the diverse challenges posed by varying climatic and vegetative conditions is crucial for crafting effective wildfire management plans.

2. The juxtaposition of human settlements with wildland vegetation in a wildland-urban interface area creates a distinct wildfire risk profile when compared to remote wilderness regions. In the wildland-urban interface, where homes are interspersed with natural vegetation, prioritizing community preparedness and establishing defensible space around residential structures emerges as a crucial strategy to mitigate wildfire hazards. By emphasizing proactive measures such as fuel reduction, buildings hardening, and community evacuation planning, residents can enhance their resilience to wildfire and reduce the likelihood of property loss and human casualties.

Conversely, in remote wilderness areas without significant human settlement, the focus shifts to maintaining ecosystem resilience and maintaining natural fire regimes. Prioritizing the ecological health of these wilderness areas means allowing wildfires to play their natural role in shaping landscapes, promoting biodiversity, and rejuvenating ecosystems. By embracing the concept of fire as a natural ecological process, land managers can work to restore and maintain the balance of native vegetation, wildlife habitat, and overall ecosystem health.

3. In regions where wildfires have been rare occurrences or have been effectively suppressed for extended periods, historical data on fire behaviour and impacts may be scarce, unreliable, or non-existent. This lack of historical information poses a significant challenge in evaluating baseline risks and establishing pragmatic targets for fuel reduction, prescribed burning, and other risk reduction strategies. Without a robust dataset to draw upon, assessing the potential impacts of wildfires becomes a complex and uncertain endeavour. The lack of historical context hinders the ability to accurately predict fire behaviour, understand vegetation dynamics, and anticipate the ecological consequences of uncontrolled wildfires. In such circumstances, stakeholders are faced with the formidable task of navigating a landscape where the past may offer limited guidance for the future.

The lack of comprehensive historical data complicates the task of predicting future fire behaviour and implementing targeted mitigation strategies. Moreover, a holistic approach to wildfire risk management must encompass not only ecological considerations but also socio-economic factors. Balancing the imperatives of ecological resilience with the practical realities of socio-economic dynamics presents a multifaceted challenge that requires careful navigation and strategic decision-making.

Incorporating socio-economic aspects into wildfire risk management entails setting targets that strike a delicate balance between ecological conservation and community well-being and resilience. For instance, adopting stringent fire suppression policies in fire-adapted ecosystems (less extreme wildfires) may inadvertently lead to the accumulation of fuel loads that ultimately fuel more intense fires in the long term. Therefore, a critical tool in addressing the growing wildfire crisis is to manage wildfires so that they burn safely under low and moderate conditions. Addressing this dilemma requires making informed decisions that prioritize both short-term community safety and long-term ecological sustainability. Finding the optimal equilibrium between immediate protective measures and sustainable ecosystem management necessitates making trade-offs and considering the interconnectedness of ecological, social, and economic factors.

As stakeholders grapple with the complexities of wildfire risk management, it becomes evident that a nuanced and inclusive approach is essential (justice aspect). By recognising the intricate interactions between ecological health, community resilience, and economic viability, decision-makers can develop strategies that promote sustainable coexistence with wildfire (integrated fire management) while protecting both natural environments and human livelihoods. Adopting this holistic perspective is key to effectively addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by wildfires and forging a path towards resilient and harmonious landscapes.

2.1 Wildfire risk management (WFRM) as a complex multi-stakeholder challenge

Integrated WFRM depends on political, legal and cultural framework conditions, including the complex interplay of different stakeholders involved in prevention, preparedness, response and recovery. Discussions on the questions of who is actually part of the wildfire risk management community are ongoing and might be responded differently depending on context and mandate. As far as the WFRM IAs funded under the EU Green Deal are concerned, the clustering activities of stakeholders has resulted in the following list of key actors⁸:

- **Emergency management organisations**, e.g., firefighters, civil protection, medical services and police, first responders performing operations in the field, fire analysts, forest services.
- **Scientific community**, e.g., research and academic institutions involved in diverse scientific areas related to wildfire management, fire safety engineers, forest services.
- **Policy making bodies**, e.g., administrations acting at different territorial levels, EU law and policymakers, national and local politicians.
- **Land management groups**, e.g., landowner associations, land planners, farmers, foresters, whose activity has direct implications over fuel load management through burning, cutting, grazing and other activities.
- **Environmental associations**, e.g., conservation organisations, environmental consultancies, environmental educators.
- **Media**, e.g., journalists, communicators in the environmental field; social media influencers.
- **Society**, e.g., social groups, volunteer associations, representatives for certain citizen groups, vulnerable groups.
- **Industry, technology, and innovation**, e.g., the industry around sectors of energy, construction, infrastructures, timber, technologies, fire prevention and firefighting equipment; Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance industry.

This overview of stakeholders with different mandates and objectives towards managing wildfire risk already shows that developing integrated multi-stakeholder strategies is not an easy task. Measures that are considered right by one stakeholder may counteract the activities by another or be perceived as unjust in terms of responsibilities or costs related to them. At the same time, risk perception should be considered in risk mitigation planning as it aligns strategies with stakeholders' concern and behaviours and ensure that interventions are more effective and accepted, especially at local level. Martin et al. (2009) highlighted the importance of understanding the risk perception from the community by policy makers in order to use the most effective policy tools for risk communication to motivate risk reduction behaviours in citizens. But not only aspects of how risk is actually distributed but also procedural justice in terms of who is actually heard in risk management processes can play a role in developing such approaches.⁹ More generally, aspects of governance and participation can play a role. For example:

- Who was involved in the development of strategies and who was not and why (not)?
- Who is responsible for what?
- Who gets to define what is prioritised for protective measures: local communities, government officials, majority consensus?

⁸ More information about the clustering can be found in Firelogue D7.2 "Stakeholder Clustering Report".

⁹ More detailed reflections on justice aspects in managing wildfire risk can be found in Firelogue D4.1 "Just Transition Concept Review and Adaptation for Firelogue".

- What is the procedure to be followed for deciding the protective measures should be prioritised (e.g., conservation oriented or traditional fire-suppression investments)?
- Who should be responsible for recovering wildfire losses?

Other examples of justice aspects that arise in developing WFRM measures and strategies can relate to land-use restrictions that relocate people and their homes from wildfire-prone areas will put fewer lives at risk:

- But at whose expense?
- What is the liability of those whose actions increase fire risk and exposure?
- How does prevention balance the tension between individual responsibility or public solidarity?

Far from exhaustive, these questions already open the door to the challenges described below. Different interpretations and understandings can lead to disagreements and require conflict negotiation processes (prioritising between, for example, conservation and management when it comes to implementing fire prevention measures). Consequently, the specification of WFRM targets and the ways to achieve them are complex and engage controversial processes very much linked with a range of contextual factors of governance, culture, legal systems and other aspects that need to be considered and require for multi-stakeholder discussions.

2.2 The normative dimension: desirability of targets

The specified Green Deal expected impacts are grounded in abstract goals, pointing to areas where WFRM can have a real and concrete impact. However, these targets can be quite controversial in terms of their desirability and feasibility when taking a closer look. Making explicit the underlying assumptions of stakes and benefits matter for assessing impacts. What is prioritised or de-emphasised in different approaches to achieving the numbers has real, and often differential and political, consequences across societies, ecosystems, and governance processes. They also have the potential to place responsibility in different hands.

For example, zero fatalities from wildfires is usually a set target that society aims to achieve and is always the priority in risk management incl. response strategies. However, unfortunately, it is likely that despite such endeavours, fatalities may persist – due to the increasing intensity of fires and diverse human behaviours, despite implemented policies and education programs. Relating this impact to firefighters, an opportunity to reduce respective fatalities would be to not intervene in certain (high intensity) fires or parts of them. In parallel, firefighting resources may be allocated where they will be most effective at protecting lives, not necessarily where property losses are most likely (see also Australasian Fire Authorities Council 2005). However, this may come at the costs of properties and potentially related infrastructures that will be highly damaged. Simultaneously, a respective strategy will increase emissions, economic costs, as houses and properties will be burnt, thus insurances or states have to cover the recovery and/or reconstruction costs. Moreover, longer-term health burdens due to air quality or water pollution resulting from fire events need to be considered to entirely achieve a “zero fatalities” target. It is hence crucial to discuss *how* these targets are to be achieved and what is the priority level of the targets. This would support decision making during wildfire suppression operations, e.g., if the target “50% reduction in building losses” has a higher priority than “Control of any extreme and potentially harmful wildfire in less than 24 hours” firefighters should focus their effort on preserving building rather than trying to control the fire as soon as possible.

Similarly, controlling an extreme wildfire in less than 24 hours raises a series of questions about feasibility and desirability. First, what level of resources are necessary and available to fight such fires, addressing both their size and severity? Second, what are the requirements to keep up with dynamic

and evolving fire suppression needs, as fires increase in intensity, and jump current break-line techniques? Third, what are the impacts of achieving this goal beyond suppression of fire? Firefighters use a variety of techniques and equipment and they can often gain control over a fire within a matter of hours. These techniques include fire breaks and firefighting retardants. Is it feasible to meet this target without damaged ecosystems? How does putting resources into re-balancing ecosystems to burn cooler – so less chemicals are needed -- fit into activities for this target?

Finally, it raises fundamental questions about what classifies a wildfire as “extreme”, continuing existing challenges regarding terminology across WFRM experts (Prat-Guitart and Ghermandi 2020). For example, Tedim et al. (2018) define extreme wildfire events focusing on the physical factors of fire behaviour that influence the capacity to control the fire as compared to studies that understand extreme events rather relational to historic fire patterns (e.g. Bowman et al. 2019). Building on Tedim et al. (2018), recent research proposes that “Extreme Wildfire Events (EWE) are defined as wildfires with large-scale complex interactions between fire and atmosphere generating pyroconvective behaviour, coupling processes, that results in fast, intense, uncertain, and fast-paced changing fire behaviour” (Castellnou et al. 2022).

When can a fire be said to be under “control”? Is allowing fires to burn in case of a wildfire within a control zone away from people while allowing smoke to move into areas where people live considered a desirable approach to the target? These are important questions and depending on how we answer them, measures to reach one target might even contradict measures to achieve other expected targets. Persistence on controlling any wildfire in less than 24 hours by any means may, for example, render the target of “no fatalities” unfeasible since it might put responders at risk of an event that is actually uncontrollable. Moreover, it raises similar challenges as the “fire paradox” which puts in tension a focus on minimising burnt area with minimising fire impacts (whereby the larger area left unburnt from successful suppression raises the risk scenario for the following fire campaign). Overall, it is important to understand the decision whether or not the fire can be controlled depends very much on prevention and restoration efforts. Only resilient and resistant forests shaped by pre- and post-fire intervention such as thinning, pre-scribed burning, creating natural tree barriers will determine the controllability of a fire¹⁰.

Similar questions could be asked about how to achieve the increase of insured losses from wildfires. Research on the societal impact of insurance on how people live in relation to hazards has shown that insurance has the potential exacerbating social inequalities when it comes to access to insurance coverage. Insurance companies exclude certain areas from their insurance coverage or request very high premiums. In addition, insurance for (economically used) forest areas that includes wildfires (including those caused by humans e.g. a cigarette or an electrical wire, not just those caused by natural causes like lightning) is not yet widely available across Europe, notably not in wildfire-prone countries like Portugal, Italy and Greece, where the government tends to step in on an ad-hoc basis to support victims financially. In this way, insurance practices make it possible for the wealthy to afford insurance and the related necessary high-quality buildings. Similar can be said for some high-risk wildfire zones, like the wealthy city of Malibu in California, which have a high likelihood of burning and being rebuilt every quarter-century on a mix of public and insurance funds, which has, some argued, encouraged continued (re)building in these high-risk zones and taking resources from more impoverished areas (Davis 2022). This raises a series of questions around what kinds of insurance are

¹⁰ A deliverable of SILVANUS was submitted in March 2023, that describes innovative concepts on forest management.

desirable and whether the coverage should be provided by private companies or state coverage¹¹. Similarly, it suggests further considerations as to what losses should be covered, what schemes should become an obligation, what incentives should be spotlighted, and which legal restrictions and requirements in terms of building exist and interplay with insurance schemes.

In summary, the focus on a final target can make it harder to identify the important, but less clearly related underlying determinants or normative questions. However, the underlying prerequisites or potential approaches as well as the related trade-offs and tensions between actions across these targets need to be made explicit. Since most of the expected targets are highly normative and affect different types of stakeholders in differing ways, they also bring along matters of justice between these stakeholder groups and different types of impacts in terms of risk distribution, vulnerability and coping measures. Taking these multi-stakeholder challenges into consideration and allowing to integrate different views would additionally require for broader societal debate about the targets and ways to achieve them.

2.3 Specification of targets

In addition to this general debate about societal wildfire risk related developments, further specification of the targets is needed with respect to potential measures contributing to a target, the impact of those measures, and their underlying justice dimensions. Even the same target, as it is mediated across different actors and users, can be related to different expectations across different social and professional settings (Fiore-Gartland and Neff 2015). Documenting, negotiating, and communicating these expectations are as important as the definition of the target, data gathering, and meta-data practices themselves for explaining and validating how they support the intended targets (Dourish and Gomez Cruz 2018).

In some cases, it is not readily obvious how to translate a concept – and all its variations -- into actionable, quantifiable, measures. For example, to address the call for ‘50% of Natura 2000 protected areas to be fire-resilient’ we must first answer – and agree upon -- What are the parameters that makes an area to be (considered) fire resilient? Then there needs to be consensus on how that definition can be measured. In terms of fatalities, it could be questioned whether the target relates to direct or indirect fatalities, to first responders, citizens, tourists or all of them. Additionally, should the damage caused to firefighter’s mental health be considered as wildfire could lead to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression and generalised anxiety (To et al. 2021)?

One way to determine potential targets is the identification of target areas. The above-mentioned Green Deal targets can thereby serve as an example. However, each dimension needs to be accompanied with a range of questions that need to be answered jointly by the stakeholders. Making use of the example of the reduction of emissions from wildfires, a specification could address the following questions:

- What (about) emissions should be measured, and how frequently?
- Which geographic spread should be measured?
- Who and how do the emissions impact those affected?
- How can they be physically measured in different environments?
- What activities can support the reduction of emissions? (This should also include their relative impact on that reduction)

¹¹ Wild fire risk insurance isn’t necessarily an interesting market for insurers from a business perspective. Public insurance systems like the French or the Spanish ones may be an alternative example to consider in recommending larger insurance coverage while they also bring their own down-sides such as state monopolies.

- How do these activities differ across member states?

Specifically, does reduction focus on readily measured gases (such as CO₂) with a focus on longer term climate impacts? Or does it focus on particle size and harder to measure toxic emissions emerging from burning human infrastructure that impact more acutely human health? Should measurements focus on average reductions over a region or more local reductions in places carrying a disproportionate impact (which are often in communities least socio-economically able to address the impacts and with the least ability to voice their needs)? Even the rate at which measurements are taken can provide different results (especially as a fire burns over different objects and plumes are dispersed by air currents).

For each target, a definition would have to be determined which can also be related to indicators and proxies that could serve in measuring this target like Table 1 suggests:

Table 1: Example of potential specification of Green Deal WFRM emission reduction target

Green Deal WFRM Target	Definition	Measuring the target	Potential project KPIs to assess the IA's target contribution
55% reduction in emissions from wildfires	<p>There is a wide range of contaminants that could be in theory assessed. Some of them are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions 2. Carbon monoxide (CO) 3. Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions 4. Methane (CH₄), etc. 	<p>A consistent source of data at European scale can be GFAS, but although it provides data consistent in space and time, it might be too coarse to measure the emissions of a small fire event.</p> <p>For selected case studies, using data from nearby meteorological stations could be an option, but the information will be limited and difficult to replicate in other areas and other fire events, due to potential differences in distance between the meteorological station and the fire, the direction and velocity of the winds during the fire event, etc.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. % reduction in levels of CO₂ emissions on selected areas such as case studies 2. % reduction in detection latency of the fire between the first detection and the launching of the initial attack 3. % of fires extinguished in the initial attack, before reaching 1 hectare 4. Number of Member States introducing fire-resilient considerations

A suggestion for a specification of all exemplary Green Deal targets can be found in Annex I.

Finally, it has to be stressed that several approaches to specifying targets can be taken. We have described above an upside-down approach defining the target dimensions first which would then be complemented by discussions around potential indicators in a second step. However, the identification of indicators in a first step and the extrapolation of targets in a second step is also an opportunity. Overall, it is important to note that only some targets can be directly determined by anthropogenic activity, such as the area of prescribed burns, the area managed for wildfire prevention, km of tracks maintained for emergency teams access etc. Other targets such as fatalities, number of wildfires, area affected or emissions can only indirectly be affected by WFRM measures.

2.4 Scale of actioning target values

A final challenge related to the Green Deal WFRM targets is that they lack any specification of what geographic scale should be the focus of the targets. It is not clear at which level the targets are to be monitored and it remains unclear whether the targets should be achieved at country or EU scale (or any other scale). The three WFRM IAs work on their case studies and apply their innovation at a local scale. The scale of the target, in addition to being key to appropriate specification and data identification, affects attribution of responsibility for achieving the targets.

Scale additionally matters on how data becomes evidence for a target. Some data may be available at local level only (such as prescribed burns or damaged buildings for example) and would have to be aggregated, extrapolated, or simulated at the national level for further comparison at EU level. However, little data is currently available at national and EU level to support these necessary scalar frameworks. While some countries have assembled a more extensive fire related database with a deeper history of firefighting in their region, others have little data available or have little data that speaks directly to their contextual considerations. The targets themselves imply different levels of data: ignition and building damage are locally monitored events while data related to fatalities and prescribed fires are collected rather at regional or even national. Mixing scales across the targets could require different, yet simultaneous, approaches to assessment of success and impact.

Scale also matters for attributions of responsibility. If the targets are at the EU scale, could disproportionately high wildfire emission savings balance any increase in another country (can one country's over-achievement counter another's under-achievement)? Similarly, are the burdens of target achievement to be shared evenly across Member States or would an equitable approach, requesting more intense efforts from more affected states be an alternative way, potentially balanced by some form of compensation mechanism?

Overall, if the scale is too broad, it could miss local nuances in WFRM, such as how electrical infrastructures are maintained could impact fire ignitions or how smog can be trapped to the ground by inversions affecting some with air pollution from fires more than others. If the scale is too local it can become difficult to identify the necessary comparisons and trends to assess national and EU level efforts or transfer lessons from one area to another.

Overall, the process of estimating and assessing the scalability of the solutions and their EU wide impact is very challenging. Specifically, questions of scale raise a series of uncertainties in this process:

- Are the targets to be addressed separately by each individual region or country or across the EU as a whole?
- Should responsibilities be spread equally or equitably across the regions?
- Is moving between scales done via multiplication, extrapolation, or using separate data sets per scale? Should these approaches be homogenized or not?

Finally, it will be challenging to determine the attribution of the impact of specific WFRM measures or technologies (or projects) towards the expected targets. Innovation Actions are developing impact assessment methodologies at case study or project level focusing on qualitative and quantitative assessments regarding efficiencies and effectiveness for the user. These approaches need to be integrated and harmonised with the broader Green Deal targets to allow for a comparison of the potential wider impact of WFRM measures and approaches.

3 Assessing progress towards defined targets

3.1 Availability of data sets

In addition to engaging in further defining the intentions, societal benefits, and accepted impacts of a target, data is needed to support monitoring actions towards them. Before any new data-based system can offer value, these starting questions about providing data and agreeing upon its relevance as evidence needs to be dealt with.

Questions have long been raised about what makes “good enough” data and how data relates to evidence for environmental and humanitarian problems (Gabrys et al. 2016; ACAPS 2014; Oxfam et al. 2007). Even longer studies have been made, discussing the complexity of counting, from what counts as eligible data points to systems of registration and verification, and how they relate to networks of trust (Martin and Lynch 2014). Much of this relies on what data is classified (often politically and contested) as evidence for a target, as already implied by the challenges of target specification.

As much, the ability to make a claim relates to the ability to represent that element with data; acts which require the existence of data that are fit for purpose. For example, the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) has been appointed by the European Council and Parliament (European Parliament 2003; 2006) to be in charge of the development and implementation of methods for the evaluation of forest fire danger and burned area mapping. As part of these regulations, the European Union Member States have the mandate to provide data to EFFIS related to first alert, first intervention and extinction date and time; location of the outbreak; total fire damaged area; breakdown of the fire-damaged area into forest and other wooded land and non-forested areas; and presumed cause of the fire. These data potentially cover the targets related to fire duration and causes of fires, but do not address the rest of the targets.

EFFIS also publishes, on a yearly basis, a report on Forest Fires in Europe, Middle East and North Africa (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al. 2020) where the different countries, on a voluntary basis, provide a summary of the fires occurred in the previous years, their characteristics and impacts, and the fire prevention and extinction activities performed. These reports provide some additional information regarding the targets, such as fatalities, fire causality, and in some cases, and only for a few countries, also include data on monetary losses from wildfires or prescribed fires. However, since the provision of data for these reports is voluntary, not all countries provide this information, and it is not possible to assure that the information is complete.

Data availability for each country may vary depending on the country's fire management system. Some countries may have more comprehensive and up-to-date data available, while others may have less complete information. Some data are near real-time, some take months to process for impact analysis, and some are designed to support forecasting.

Programmes like Copernicus or Eumetsat provide earth observation (EO) data for wildfire monitoring, which have the advantage of being consistent both in time and in space across Europe. This EO information includes active fires and burned area, with temporal resolutions from less than an hour in the case of geostationary satellites to daily and weekly in the case of polar orbiting satellites. But this temporal resolution is usually inversely related to the spatial resolution: the data available every 15 minutes from the SEVIRI instrument onboard Meteosat Second Generation is available at around 3 km spatial resolution, while the information provided by the Sentinel-2 MSI instruments has 10 or 20 m

spatial resolution, but with a frequency of once every 5 days. EFFIS, in its Current Situation Viewer¹² uses some of these EO data to provide daily updated information on active fires and burned area.

In the case of fire emissions, ground-based air quality monitoring is generally sparse. Much air quality is not monitored through direct data due to the lack of sensor stations, but via models, relying on assumptions about the characteristics of the fires and the fuel consumed by them, building upon satellite and ground data. Several models on fire emissions exist, and although they are based on some well-known general principles, their results vary depending on the input variables they use: burned area, fuels available, combustion completeness, and emission factors (Shi et al. 2015). Some widely known fire emission products are the Global Fire Emissions Database (GFED, Giglio et al. 2013), and the Global Fire Assimilation System (GFAS, Kaiser et al. 2012). EFFIS, as part of its Statistical Portal, offers seasonal trends for the fires of approximately 30 ha or larger, for all European countries, and for different contaminants, based on GFAS v1.2. Still, in recent years new advances have shown that the emissions previously calculated have been underestimated, due to an underestimation of the area burned (Ramo et al. 2021) and to the use of combustion completeness and available fuels parameters that have been improved based on new field data (van Wees et al. 2022). This implies that data exist to quantify the emissions from fires target, but their uncertainty is high.

Data availability challenges are exacerbated by issues around data ownership. Information about insurance coverage, for instance, is frequently only available through insurers, for purchase. Similarly, information on building damage can be retrieved in some countries within different ministries, in charge of different damage assessment programmes of private and public buildings, at post- or pre-disaster basis. Building quality and vulnerability data is even further distributed. Another source of information on buildings are the statistical authorities of the countries.

Apart from data availability, another issue can be the consistency between countries. Each country can have their own way of describing these data, which can be gathered using different standards (relevant to the local needs) that make comparisons difficult. Some measures have been taken at European level to deal with this; a good example is the Harmonized classification scheme of fire causes in the EU adopted for the European Fire Database of EFFIS (Camia et al. 2013), which has proposed a method for all countries to homogenize the classification of fire causes. Still, not all European countries have adopted this method, nor are some of them providing this information in a timely matter.

Data availability also requires infrastructures and frameworks for sharing upstream and across borders. The data comes in a variety of formats, gathered at different frequencies and granularities, using different classification systems, employing different meta-data standards, which further increases the challenges for the creation of a common baseline. Some has to be gathered via resource intensive means, even collected by hand. Even more resources need to go into making them comparable or combinable to express the complexity and layers within each target. This suggests that understanding how targets are met and the impacts of choices made to define success have to be considered (and potentially limited) in relation to data availability. Finally, building evidence towards the targets requires resources to:

- A) action the necessary activities
- B) gather and process the data to act as evidence for that activity
- C) archive and store the data for future use and historical comparison.

¹² https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/apps/effis_current_situation/, accessed on May 2023.

3.2 Baseline data for assessing success

The Green Deal call suggested that the impacts are to be achieved as compared to 2019 values. However, since the target dimensions have not been assessed in the past, no baseline dataset is available. Defining a baseline raises challenges, as does the specification of the targets and data availability, in that the baselines have to be built on existing data, which may not represent the current specifications and actions defined for the targets. On top of this, frequently the legal frameworks for mandatory documentation and data storage are lacking. For example, no legal mandate exists for the countries to provide consistent information on fatalities, building losses, insurance against fire damages or prescribed fires.

Only the year 2019 as the baseline may however not be sufficiently representative of fire occurrence in Europe. This is because 2019 had a below-average number of fires and burned area in some countries (e.g. Portugal, Greece), while at the same time having the highest fire occurrence in others (e.g. France, Romania) compared to the previous years. For this reason, it was considered that using average or median values from a series of years could be more representative. For the baseline assessment, a 10-year period ending in 2019 (i.e. 2010-2019) was considered to be more representative of the fire occurrence in Europe. Although a longer period would, in principle, be better, the farther in time, the less information is available for many targets. However, at the same time, a longer period might be misleading as wildfires have significantly increased in frequency and intensity in Southern Europe¹³, affecting also areas not prone to wildfires, like Central and Northern Europe¹⁴.

Pettinari (2022) proposed a baseline assessment at European level based on information available from European institutions, in order to assure as much as possible, the consistency of the data. When available, these data have been extracted from the EFFIS databases and reports (as in the case of fatalities, accidental fire ignitions, emissions and fire duration). Still, and as indicated in the previous section, many times these data are not fully consistent, or are lacking for some countries and/or some years. In the case of the losses from wildfires insured target, the European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority (EIOPA) database was used, but only very generic information on Gross Written Premiums (GWP) covering fire damages were available, and for this reason an indirect target (GDP per population) was proposed. In the cases of building losses and prescribed fires, not sufficient data were available to develop a baseline at European level.

Finally, with respect to the target related to Natura 2000 protected areas to be fire resilient, not only there is no consistent information available on the “level” of resilience of these protected areas (since different authors define and measure resilience taking into consideration diverse objective and assumptions), but there is also no established threshold defined in the literature to divide the landscape into “resilient” and “not resilient” areas. As such, only an increase or decrease of resilience could be evaluated in the pilot sites proposed by the IAs, and considering only the aspects of resilience that can be modified by human intervention (e.g. land management practises). Another possibility would be to target an increase of the number of Natura 2000 sites that incorporate fire management in their protected area plans. This should include practices that focused more on prevention rather than on suppression and promote the reintroduction of the natural fire regime of the area, e.g., by prescribed burning. Nonetheless, this might not be sufficient to strictly classify landscapes in “resilient” or “not-resilient”, expert judgement might be used to evaluate the efficiency of the fire management plan of the area.

¹³ <https://www.eumetsat.int/southern-europe-battles-increases-major-wildfires>

¹⁴ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/forest-fires-in-europe>

4 Discussion

This paper portrayed the lack of policy targets in the wildfire risk management domain and the lack of a binding legal framework at EU level more specifically. However, it also showed that the development of a legal framework or binding targets is challenging but possible. Targets provide clear and measurable goals that help guide and assess the effectiveness of policies and strategies and facilitate a shared understanding. At the same time, their development requires for normative discussions around what would actually be desirable, just and reasonable.

In addition, developed targets need to be monitored to understand the impact of political action and additional efforts needed and to take informed decisions in feedback loops. In order to monitor progress on targets, an encompassing data base is needed. At the European Union level, initiatives such as the EU Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) but also national databases and systems provide a measure for reporting and monitoring wildfire activity. However, data availability highly differs between EU Member States and hence, wildfires, their ignition sources (natural vs. human) and their impacts in terms of losses are sometimes difficult to analyse and to compare across countries. The adoption, and use, of a uniform and standardised, potentially even obligatory data collection procedure across EU Member States, considering potential targets that should be measured and monitored, would allow to effectively create a baseline that could be used at EU level but that would also be required for the monitoring of the Sendai Framework.

This challenge also points to justice related questions around the level of implementing potential targets: do European targets make sense and would they have to be reached collectively, i.e. by a negotiated “fair” share per country? But how could a fair contribution be designed, i.e. according to GDP or size of the country or forested area? Or are target contributions to be shared evenly per Member State?

These are just some of the questions that may have to be addressed at European scale as wildfire related losses increase. Becoming aware of challenges or even trade-offs is important for the development of policies, specifically at EU level. They show that in many cases a “one fits all” solution will not work but the facilitation of multi-stakeholder negotiation processes at European level and the identification of diverse interests and needs are key to designing integrated strategies.

Overall, the paper has portrayed a number of aspects that need to be considered when developing wildfire risk management targets at the European scale. These encompass:

- Careful analysis of **stakeholders** in wildfire risk management that should be involved in the governance process
- Discourse around the **desirability of targets** (and specifically for certain values) is needed in order to consider all perspectives and relevant implications
- Measuring potential targets requires for the specification of **definitions**, and review of available **data sets** and Key Performance Indicators as well as suitable base line data
- Defining the **scale of implementing potential targets** and the potential burden sharing between regions and countries

5 Conclusion

New wildfire risk reports and policy frameworks call for more integrated wildfire management and suggest advances in prevention measures and financing structure among others. However, specifically targets as a transparent and motivating measures to advance policy fields are mainly lacking so far, including the European context. This specifically worrying since examples like the Flood and Seveso III Directives have shown that advances are possible. At the same time, wildfire related losses are

increasing and since this trend is expected to be continued, it may only be a matter of time until the need for more concrete requirements or targets will become pressing.

Related to that expected need, we have detailed the challenges but also opportunities that relate to the formulation of targets and their measurability while proposing a range of questions that could be considered in their development. Since the wildfire risk management field is already characterised by its complexity and multitude of stakeholders, it can be expected that any process relating to the formulation and monitoring of targets will be complex and time-consuming. This paper hence aims to encourage the discussion about the usefulness and applicability of a more binding legal wildfire risk management framework or binding targets as soon as possible.

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ANNEX: Suggested expected impacts definitions and potential indicators (work in progress)

Green Deal Target	Definition	Measuring the target	Potential KPIs to assess their target contribution
0 fatalities from wildfires	Fatalities are defined as those that would not have otherwise occurred, if there had not been a wildfire. This includes direct fatal casualties (in the fire), as well as any indirect fatalities as a result of injuries caused by a wildfire incident. Even if the casualty dies at a later date, any fatality whose cause is attributed to a wildfire is included.	Number of fatalities; however, the data is not always easily available. Specifically, fatalities that occur with a time-lag to the disaster event are difficult to grasp, especially those related to smoke – or other pollutants – inhalation, which could cause the death even months after the fire, and can be associated with comorbidities such as asthma or other lung diseases, young age, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of engaged people participating in trainings, exchanges, awareness activities • Number of fire fighters trained • Number of awareness campaigns and real-time emergency workshops • Number of fire danger scenarios reviewed from historical and fictional case-studies
50% reduction in accidental fire ignitions	Human-caused wildfires as result of accidental (not intentional) ignition sources are ignitions that were not intentional, and can be altered through prevention efforts. In these fire ignitions, all human causes (electrical network, railroad, campfire, smoking, fire use, candles, cooking/electrical appliances, equipment, railroad, juveniles, farm machinery etc.) are included.	Ignition causes; however, this information is in several countries not available or incomplete, since ignition sources are not (always) analysed and documented.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of accidental fire causes evaluated • Number of demonstration activities on accidental fire ignitions • Number of awareness campaigns and real-time emergency workshops • Number of WUI homeowners informed
55% reduction in emissions from wildfires	<p>There is a wide range of contaminants that could be in theory assessed. Some of them are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions 2. Carbon monoxide (CO) 3. Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions 4. Methane (CH₄), etc. 	<p>A consistent source of data at European scale can be GFAS, but although it provides data consistent in space and time, it might be too coarse to measure the emissions of a small fire event.</p> <p>For selected case studies, using data from nearby meteorological stations could be an option, but the information will be limited and difficult to replicate in other areas and other fire events, due to potential differences in distance between the meteorological station and the fire, the direction and velocity of the wind during the fire event, etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % reduction in levels of CO₂ emissions on selected areas such as case studies • % reduction in detection latency of the fire between the first detection and the launching of the initial attack • % of fires extinguished in the initial attack, before reaching 1 hectare • Number of Member States introducing fire-resilient considerations

Green Deal Target	Definition	Measuring the target	Potential project KPIs to assess their target contribution
Control of any extreme and potentially harmful wildfire in less than 24 hours	Control is the process of completely suppressing the combustion in the perimeter of the wildfire. Control occurs by removing one of the three ingredients fire needs to burn: heat, oxygen, or fuel, within 24 hours since the recording of the initial ignition time. Harmful wildfires are those that can potentially become social, economic and environmental disasters.	It is difficult to properly define "harmful": what threshold should be used to determine if a fire can develop into a disaster ¹⁵ ? The time between detection of the fire (recording of the ignition time) and the time of control is usually recorded in the fire reports. This information is provided to EFFIS as part of the annual reporting of each country. Still, not all reports are accurate, some with start or control time missing, date but not time recorded, fire events missing, etc. ¹⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● % decrease in response time of fire fighters ● Number of different fire suppression types to be evaluated ● Number of deployments of different command centres to tackle the origin of a fire ● Number of demonstrations on training scenarios curated for worst-case scenario and fire simulators ● % reduction in time lapses for data provision to support the end-users in controlling wildfires in <24h ● Number of response collaborations with international platforms ● Number of users of response systems ready

¹⁵ What is more, a fire can become harmful in less than 24 hours, as proved by the fires of October 2017 in Portugal, where 244,000 hectares were burned in 10 hours, causing 51 fatalities.

¹⁶ Personal communication from EFFIS personnel compiling fire reports from countries.

Green Deal Target	Definition	Measuring the target	Potential project KPIs to assess their target contribution
50% of Natura 2000 protected areas to be fire-resilient	<p>Officially declared Natura 2000 areas as well as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fire resilience based on the geographical coverage area • Fire-resistant ecosystems by promoting the resilience of old-growth forests or by adapting young forest under natural evolution to expected climate change impacts, optimizing protection and provision functions in managed areas <p>It is important to define fire-resilience. Here are proposed two options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adaptive resilience</i> to wildfire centres on managing both the human and non-human environment in response to changing climate and fire regimes and increasing wildfire risks and exposure of human communities; • <i>Transformative-resilience</i> requiring a profound shift in the human relationship with the environment and the wildfires, that embraces the dynamic and rapidly changing role of fire in social ecological systems (McWethy et al, 2019) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The spatial distribution of the Natura 2000 areas is clear and can be downloaded from the European Environmental Agency website. <p>As shown in the column to the left, several definitions of resilience exist, and depending on which is adopted, a region could be deemed as resilient or not.</p> <p>What is more, usually the term “resilience” as a comparison between the same ecosystem in two points in time, or as a comparison between two different ecosystems, to state if one is “more” or “less” resilient than the other, but not clear threshold exists to classify an ecosystem as resilient or not.</p> <p>For these reasons, it is quite challenging to directly measure the target in a consistent way.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of demonstrations for enhanced resilience across IAs pilots. • Number of Natura 2000 managing entities reached regarding respective activities. • Number of Nature 2000 protected areas related to the projects developing a fire prevention plan.
50% reduction in building losses	<p>A building is a structure with a roof and walls, such as a house or factory.</p> <p>Structural loss means any loss as a result of wildfire ignitions.</p>	<p>There is no consistent source of information on building losses across Europe. Although some countries inform monetary losses in the yearly report of EFFIS, these also include other losses not related to buildings (e.g. timber, public infrastructures, etc.). These data is provided by country, but not disaggregated per region or fire event.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of case studies related to the reduction of building losses • Number of Member States introducing urban planning regulations for risk prevention and mitigation

Green Deal Target	Definition	Measuring the target	Potential project KPIs to assess their target contribution
90% of losses from wildfires insured	Types of insured losses include home property, garage, tool shed, belongings, vehicles, businesses, etc. and anything else that can be insured.	The information on insured losses is not available from the different Insurance Companies. The data available in a consistent way, from EIOPA ¹⁷ , only provides information on the line of business "Fire Prop", which includes fires that damage properties, but it also includes structural fires (not only vegetation fires), and other sources of damages to properties, such as explosions, storms, theft, etc. This information is only available disaggregated by country, and does not differentiate between properties that could be susceptible to wildfires (i.e. those located in the WUI or in rural areas), and those located in urban areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of insurance schemes considered ● Number of insurance companies working on offering catastrophe bonds related to the project ● Number of insurance companies interested in the IAs insurance solutions ● Number of campaigns to inform the public ● Number of new policies proposals to legislators
25% increase in surface area of prescribed fire treatments at European (EU) level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prescribed fire treatments include the planned use of fire to achieve precise and clearly defined objectives. ● Introduced in some countries in Southern Europe¹⁸ to control fire regimes by managing fuels, counteracting the disappearance of biomass-consuming practices and reducing the fire risks inherent in highly flammable forests and shrublands. ● The primary objective prescribed burning is to reduce risks to human and natural assets via modifications of fire behaviour, although prescribed burning can be undertaken to promote ecological assets or for cultural purposes (Penman et al., 2011). 	<p>Although prescribed fires are used in some countries (e.g., Spain, Italy), these fire prevention activities are many times organized by regional authorities and not communicated to the national authorities, and no national database exists with complete information on area treated with prescribed fires.</p> <p>What is more, some countries do not allow prescribed fire treatments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of consultations of decision makers on fire-treatments ● Number of Prescribed Burning applied ● x% increase in acceptance of Prescribed Burning (No. people attending transference or training activities; Number of people informed through material and educational platforms) ● Number of regional/national legal frameworks related to Prescribed Burning in EU Member States

¹⁷ European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority.

¹⁸ It is important to note that this is not permitted by law in all Mediterranean countries.

Developing and measuring targets for reducing wildfire risk in Europe

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